

Teacher's strategies in teaching reading narrative text for the tenth graders

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- Abstract : Reading is an important ability that must be learned by students. The students will get knowledge from what they read and can increase language acquisition. The goals of this study are to find out the strategies used by the English teacher in teaching reading narrative text and to find out the student's responses to the strategies used by the English teacher in teaching reading narrative text for the tenth graders of MA Ihyaul Ulum Cangaan. The study design is descriptive qualitative. Data collection methods include; observation, questionnaire, and documentation. The data analyzed were into three parts; Data Reduction, Data display, and Drawing Conclusions or verifying. This study will focus on the English teacher and 27 tenth-grade students at MA Ihyaul Ulum Cangaan. The result showed that the English teacher employed specific techniques, such as, defining the purpose of reading, silent reading, QAR, analyzing the vocabulary, and discussion strategies. Applying these techniques, the English teacher can utilize a variety of techniques and establish new ways of teaching reading based on the subject. As a result, the teaching of reading techniques became more engaging and successful in improving students' ability to read narrative text.
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Introduction

English has become the dominant language in a wide range of activities. In Indonesia, English has become an important part of education. Mastering this language is not a simple thing to do. English is learned by the students from school to the university levels with the national curriculum that the government has set. There are four English skills; Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing. Those skills, (Harmer, 2001, p. 1999) stated that reading is a receptive skill. Receptive abilities are processing that extract meaning from the language they see or hear. Meanwhile, according to (Elizabeth et al, 20023, p. 2) reading is an ability that is highly appreciated by students and teachers. The students always get messages throughout their studies.

Reading is a crucial ability for students since it allows them to gain knowledge. By reading students also can get some information. Besides that, reading has a positive effect on students' vocabulary, spelling, and their writing. Scholars generally agree that there is a direct correlation between academic success and their engagement in reading (Alimin et al., 2023) Thus, reading is highly significant for Indonesian students due to allow them to comprehend various books published in English and get knowledge for academic objectives. Additionally, (Harmer, 2001, p. 99) stated that reading's objective is to help students grasp written languages. In addition, the reading text types must be learned by senior high school students. the types of these texts such as descriptive, narrative, analytical, recount, and so on. Teaching is an activity of the instructor assisting students to learn by sharing knowledge and experience which includes any technique that involves the students in the learning process for their learning (Halik, 2016:147). Besides that (Brown 20024 in Nurdianingsih, 2021) stated that teaching reading requires to help students become successful and efficient readers. Teaching strategy is an accurate plan for a lesson that includes structure, learner behavior, instructional goals, and implementation strategies (Antoni, 2010). It meant teaching strategies are methods for instructing the student in the learning process. The teacher must employ better techniques that strike a balance between strategy and materials. Additionally, (Ghafournia, 2023) teaching reading methods is essential in language education, particularly for enhancing reading comprehension.

Teaching reading narrative text, the English teacher may utilize a variety of techniques in teaching to properly employ any instructional style, anybody who teaches must first comprehend the concepts and assumptions that underpin each technique. (Harmer,J., 2007) strategy is an activity employed by a teacher to achieve certain teaching and learning purposes. This method may also be regarded as an overall framework for the teaching process. To engage students, instructors might utilize a kinds of technique, media, and games while teaching reading.

According to (Brown, 2007, pp. 306–310) mentioned ten strategies that English teacher may use to teach reading. They are; determining the aim of reading, using graphemic rules, silent reading skills, skimming, scanning, semantic mapping, guessing the: meaning of words, a grammatical, discourse relationship, implied meaning the lines, cultural reference, content messages; analyze vocabulary, distinguish between literal and implied meanings and the last strategy employs discourse markers to process relationship.

Meanwhile, (Allington, 2002) defined Brilliant instructors provide greater performance across curricular materials, instructional strategies, and reading programs. (Saori et al., 2024) said that Effective education involves more than just one individual passing on their expertise. Achievement instructors of reading understand that reading may be taught in a variety of methods. Teachers have to adapt their teaching to meet the requirements of their learners.

There are some previous researches on Teacher's Strategies for Teaching Reading. The first research was conducted by Muslaini (2017) titled "*Strategies for Teaching Reading Comprehension*". He determined that the English teacher employed individual learning, cooperative learning, using media, (games, images and picture series) as well as grammatical translation procedures. The second previous was done by Dwiningtiyas et al (2020) "*Teacher's Strategies in Teaching Reading Comprehension*". They discovered that the English teacher's utilized a variety of strategy in teaching reading, such as; brainstorming, reading aloud, asking for specific information, encouraging dictionary, reread for checking comprehension, and evaluating comprehension in particular tasks. Moreover, the English teacher applied and blended methods separated into three parts. The three phases were pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading stage.

Another previous research was conducted by (Setiawan, 2014) entitled "*A Study on Teacher's Strategies in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Second Grade of Student's MTS Tarbiyatul Ulum*". He determined that the teacher employed fourth strategies they are; memorization, question and answer, game and discussion technique. With these strategies the learners easily understand the text of reading comprehension.

Based on the previous above the researcher focuses on the English teacher's strategies of the tenth graders in teaching reading narrative text which aims to find out the strategies used by the English teacher in teaching reading narrative text and to find out the student's responses to the strategies used by the English teacher in teaching reading narrative text for the tenth graders of MA Ihyaul Ulum Cangaan. Because there are many problems in reading skills. they are not interested in reading, they feel a lack of vocabulary, low comprehension of text structures, and they do not understand what they read.

Methods

This research was designed a descriptive qualitative. The subject of the research is the English teacher and 27 students in the tenth grade of MA Ihyaul Ulum Cangaan. In collecting the data, the researcher used observation, questionnaire, and documentation. Additionally, Miles and Huberman model was employed in facilitating the data analysis process. Including data reduction, data display, and drawing the conclusion (Sugiyono, 2017, p. 325) The observation was from of observation sheet, then, the questionnaire was from an open-ended questionnaire sheet consisting of 25 questions. 20 questions about the strategy utilized by the English teacher and 5 questions about the student's responses to the strategy utilized by the English teacher in teaching reading. The last is documentation, which involves the lesson plan and a picture of the condition during the teaching and learning process.

Finding and Discussions

This stage displays the outcomes of the observation sheets taken from the third meeting, there are three activities in teaching reading. The first is Pre-Activity, in which the English teacher gives the opening greetings and prayer to start the learning session. Then, the English teacher checks an attendance list. After that, the English teacher gave the motivation and brainstormed with the students. The second portion is Whilst-Activity. In this period, the English teacher used four strategies from (Brown, 2007, p. 306) which one the English teacher provides an explanation about the purpose of reading. This way the students can easily understand the text and know the purpose of the text to be studied. furthermore, the English teacher uses efficient silent reading techniques for speedy understanding. Silent reading can

train students' understanding and thinking intelligence in reading to find detailed information from a text. the third is pronunciation, the English teacher teaches the pronunciation of difficult vocabulary. So, the students can pronounce vocabulary properly and correctly when they are reading aloud.

The last strategy applied by the English teacher asked the students to find the meaning word or vocabulary that they were not familiar. With this strategy, the students can increase their vocabulary in learning reading. The English teacher also used the discussion strategy in teaching reading to develop students' comprehension, and critical thinking skills, especially involving social communication with people. After that, in the Post-Activity the English teacher gives questions to students about learning narrative text. then, the English teacher ended the lesson with prayer together and the English teacher closed the lesson with a greeting. And then, the English teacher leaves the class. There are various approaches to examine students' language learning practices, including retrospective interviews, enhanced recall interviews, questionnaires, written diaries and journals, and think-aloud protocols during a learning activity. Although these methods have limits, they provide valuable insights on undetectable learning strategies.

The combined proportion of 25 questionnaire responses was calculated to evaluate students' perceptions of the reading abilities utilized by the teacher during the teaching and learning process. 27 students completed the questionnaire, which included 20 questions on the strategies used by the English teacher for teaching reading, while 5 questions about the student's responses on the strategy used by teacher in teaching reading with responses ranging from disagree, agree, and strongly agree. These items on the questionnaire were verified based on the students' knowledge gained during the learning process.

Table 1. The strategy category used by the English teacher

No.	Statements	D	A	SA
1.	The purpose of reading text	8%	38%	54%
2.	Silent reading text	4%	69%	27%
3.	Analyze vocabulary	48%	37%	15%
4.	QARs	11%	62%	27%

The most common method among twenty assertions is silent reading; in this proportion, students selected option "Disagree" 8%, "Agree" 38%, and "Strongly Agree" 54% that most of the students expressed strongly agree to explain the purpose of reading texts. While, students picked "Disagree" 48%, Agree 69%, and Strongly Agree 27%. The English teacher teaches reading by silent reading. So, the students may improve their understanding and cognitive ability in reading to obtain specific data. On the second scale, students selected "Disagree" 48%, "Agree" 37%, and "Strongly Agree" 15% for the expression Analyze vocabulary. The English teacher explains the meaning of new words to the students. As a consequence, students will improve their comprehension of terminology. The final stage is QARs. The students voted "Disagree" 11%, "Agree" 62%, and "Strongly Agree" 27%. The English teacher offered

several questions to determine how well their students understood what the teacher had taught them. Students not only read the material but also understand its content.

Table 2. Students' responses applied the strategy

No.	Statements	D	A	SA
1.	The strategy used by the teacher in learning to read narrative text is useful for reading skill	0%	58%	42%
2.	The strategy used by the teacher in learning to read narrative text makes it easier are useful for understanding the content of the text.	0%	77%	23%
3.	The strategy used by the teacher in learning reading narrative text encourages to find new vocabulary.	4%	65%	31%
4.	The strategy used by the teacher in learning to read narrative text makes feel more motivated to read.	15%	62%	23%
5.	Students are interested in the strategies used by the teacher in learning narrative text.	4%	61%	35%

Based on these statements, the researcher found that students' responses to several teacher strategies are very effective in learning reading. First, before stepping on the learning material, the teacher explains the purpose of reading the text. So, the students can know in advance the purpose of reading the text to be studied. The second strategy is silent reading. The English teacher gives a reading text in the student's book. Then, the students understand the entire content of the text. by silent reading, it can be seen that students are able to improve their comprehension skills and think critically about reading text. In addition, the English teacher also provides opportunities for students to ask questions something such as; the meaning of vocabulary, pronunciation, and the content of texts that the students are not familiar. However, the English teacher also applies a discussion strategy in the classroom to find out the students' activity in discussing.

Meanwhile, According to (Mega et al., 2019) Effective language learning strategies are crucial for students' success in language learning. By employing instructional strategies in the classroom is critical to creating a productive learning environment. Using a variety of teaching strategies and techniques, teachers may accommodate varied learning styles and abilities, stimulate students in the learning process, and foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Moreover, utilizing a variety of teaching styles will assist increase students' enthusiasm, involvement, and overall academic success. Teachers must constantly analyze and change their teaching techniques to fit the requirements of their students and provide a positive learning experience.

Conclusion

The study found that English teachers used most dominant strategies applied in teaching learning are; the purpose reading text, silent reading, analyzing vocabulary, QARs, and Discussion strategy. Teachers utilized these approaches to help students comprehend the reading content. Teachers varied their teaching approaches based on the materials and genre of

the work being studied. This made teaching reading comprehension more engaging. By implementing various kinds of teaching strategies suited to the requirements of individual students, educators can boost student involvement in material understanding. Additionally, implementing effective teaching practices in the classroom is critical for generating a dynamic and supportive learning environment that promotes student growth and development. For Future studies might focus on English teachers' techniques in a broader context. As a result, the outcome will be more beneficial and applicable across a wider area.

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